

Open Science NL

Open Research Software Advisory Panel

Meeting Notes

12 December 2025, 15:00 – 17:00 CET

Location: MS Teams

Attendees

- Ana Martinovici
- Daniel S. Katz
- Daniela Gawehns
- John Swinbank
- Karthik Ram
- Laurents Sesink
- Martine de Vos
- Mateusz Kuzak
- Morane Gruenpeter
- Santosh Ilamparuthi
- Vincent Traag
- Mark van Assem - Acting Co-Chair
- Marta Teperek (MT) - Acting Chair

Apologies

- Thomas Pronk
- Maria Cruz, Chair

Not present

- Karthik Ram

Notes

Welcome and agenda

MT welcomed everyone and started the meeting at 15.02. Minutes of the last meeting were published in Zenodo.

Update on the implementation of the OSNL Work Programme 2024-2025

MT explained that the decision letters for the Open Science Infrastructure call will be sent out before Christmas and that the assessment of proposals received in the Research on Open Science call for proposals is ongoing (decision expected in March 2026).

The grant to the Netherlands eScience Center (NLeSC) for running of the Research Software Sustainability Programme (including the fellows programme) for 5 years has been approved by the Open Science NL Steering Board and it is expected that the first initiatives will be launched by the Netherlands eScience Center in 2026.

Open Science NL Work Programme 2026-2027

MT explained that the [OSNL Work Programme 2026-2027](#) has been published. MT thanked panel members for their invaluable input on earlier versions of the programme.

Panel members who wished to receive a printed copy were asked to send their postal address to Marta.

MT explained how the panel members' comments had been addressed, providing a detailed overview of the possible alternatives explored for the "first come, first served" calls for proposals, which the panel had criticised earlier. The alternatives considered included:

- Assessment by a committee without referees
- Jury assessment
- Peer assessment by other applicants
- Lottery
- Qualitative assessment by the Office

Unfortunately, none of these options proved viable. Consequently, the OSNL Steering Board decided to proceed with the "first come, first served" format for several calls awarding smaller amounts of funding. This decision was driven by two main considerations:

1. To enable quick decisions and allow projects to start without unnecessary delays;
2. To manage the Office's and the community's capacity effectively.

Consequently, the eligibility criteria of these calls for proposals will need to be designed carefully and the quality of the proposals will have to be monitored and evaluated.

One panel member asked why there were no initiatives in the new work programme focusing specifically on research software (especially software sustainability issues). MT explained that the dedicated Software Sustainability Programme was funded in the previous work programme and will start in 2026 and last for 5 years. The NLeSC does not have the additional capacity to run more funding instruments at the moment. Furthermore, the work programme in general focuses less on specific programme lines, and tries to address common needs instead, which can then cater to all aspects of open science. For example, keeping the scope of the open science infrastructure call broad meant that proposals addressing more holistic problems, such as reproducible workflows, could easily fit within the scope of the call. If the call was split along the four programme lines, it would have been difficult for such proposals to fit only data, or only software needs. Furthermore, such a holistic approach creates sufficient room for proposals with dedicated focus on research software. There were a lot of proposals submitted focusing specifically on research software needs: ranging

from creating new open source software as an alternative to discipline-specific proprietary software, making existing open source software more sustainable, or building and improving infrastructure for research software discoverability.

Another example of such broader scope initiatives is the Mobility Programme. The initial idea for this programme came from the community consultation workshop and was originally intended for research software engineers, who might want to do exchanges to contribute to open research software projects and to gain skills while doing this. However, it seemed that other open science professionals could also benefit from such a programme, hence the scope was extended.

The Work Programme 2026-2027 addressed a few specific initiatives, e.g. for sensitive data, because Open Science NL builds upon the National Programme Open Science (NPOS) framework. Sensitive data is one of the NPOS objectives that was not addressed in the previous work programme. Initiatives focusing on citizen science and open research hardware deserve specific attention because they were underfunded (or not funded at all, in the latter case) before.

One panel member asked how skills transfer will be evaluated in the Research Software Sustainability programme. MT explained that the details of the programme and evaluation still need to be worked out, but that after each round of calls, there will be an evaluation. Panel members recognised that skills transfer (and evaluation of it) is generally difficult and depends on the context and engagement of the applicants as well.

There was also a discussion about funding for open source software as part of regular NWO funding calls. There was a concern raised that when researchers apply for grants, they can ask for money for licences for proprietary software (as part of the materials costs). However, if they want to use free and open source software, there are currently no mechanisms to contribute equivalent money for the maintenance costs of such software. MT explained that this discussion is outside of the remit of Open Science NL, because it pertains to NWO funding, but that she would investigate the possibilities for initiating such a conversation with appropriate people at NWO and get back to the panel.

Advisory panel – going forward

There were two aspects pertaining to the advisory panel going forward which needed to be discussed:

- Half of the members up for re-election (terms ends in April/May 2026)
- The Open Science NL Steering Board asked the panels for advice on whether, going forward, it is advisable to maintain separate FAIR Data and Open Research Software advisory panels, or whether - given the overlap in content and the potential synergies - it would be better to merge the two into a single advisory panel.

MT explained the situation to the panel members: if panels were merged, there would not be a need for elections in 2026, because half of the members of each panel would still serve, and this would result in a panel of about 12 members. So elections would be needed for the first time in 2027.

MT explained the considerations behind merging the panel. MT also explained that most members of the FAIR Data Advisory panels were in favour of merging the panels. They noted that advantages (synergies between the two communities, exchange of ideas and experiences, overlap between community members, content overlap, time efficiency, administration and organisational efficiency) outweighed the concerns, and that the concerns (sufficient expertise for each topic, sufficient time and space to discuss data- and software-specific issues) could be effectively managed by ensuring that the right expertise is present within the panel and that there is space for discussions about challenges specific to research data and to research software only.

Subsequently, panel members were invited to share their advice on the merge:

Advantages of the merge	Concerns about the merge
Cross-talk could be useful	Open hardware as a topic will be even more diluted if the panels are merged
Holistic approach is valuable	Initiatives pertaining to research data are much more visible and more investment has been made in data; research software lags behind and needs dedicated attention
Ways of working is similar for the two communities	There are issues which are software-specific (maintenance, sustainability)
Separating data and software is artificial, there are benefits from seeking synergies	If panels are merged, there will be less software experts present in the panel, and as a result, less expertise available to Open Science NL to learn from.
	Panels should only be merged if there are redundancies

Two members of the panel saw both pros and cons to a potential merge, but thought that the concerns could be effectively addressed by ensuring that the right expertise is present within the panel and also by setting the agenda in a way, so that there is dedicated space and time for discussions on matters which pertain solely to research data, or solely to research software. However, most members thought that this still did not address the concern of losing half the expertise. Furthermore, some thought that dedicating time in a joint meeting to data- and software-specific issues would mean less time which could be devoted to research software. Instead, panel members suggested that to foster synergies, panel members could read minutes of respective meetings, or a liaison role could be introduced (someone who attends both panels). Other panel members thought that this is the role of OSNL, not the panels itself, to seek synergies and forge the connections between the communities and ideas discussed within the panels.

Ultimately, the panel members concluded that merging the panel would mean that less expertise on research software would be available to OSNL.

One member of the panel was in favour of the merger.

One other panel member who could not be present at the meeting has shared a written note after the meeting outlining their preference for merging of the panels. The panel member thought that there were a lot of synergies and shared concerns and ties between the two communities could be tightened. In their opinion, concerns about sufficient space for software-specific issues could be effectively managed.

MT explained that regardless of the outcome, it would be important to look at the profiles of the panel members. MT asked panel members to complete the doodle poll to find a new date for a meeting in 2026 where the profiles and the future plans could be discussed.

MT explained that the advice of the Open Research Software panel (and of the FAIR Data panel) will be shared with the Open Science NL Steering Board. The Board will meet 21 January. The panels will be updated about the decision of the Board.

Meeting close

MT closed the meeting at 16.30.